

THE ROLE OF LITERATURE AND CULTURE IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: It is clearly known that literature is generally used in English Language Teaching (ELT) for the development of knowledge about the language. It helps the learners to get familiar with the sociopolitical backgrounds of target language society and also makes them understand how communication takes place in a particular community. Ideal literary text with good quality can stimulate the language learning among the readers and it can elicit a wide range of responses from the learners which are facilitating for language learning.

Keywords: Literature, culture, literary texts, advantages of literature, skills, traditional, criteria.

Introduction

Literature helps to develop the learner's linguistic performance because it arouses their zeal and keeps in them an ever ready inclination to read. Moreover, it helps the learners to develop fluency and the ability to comprehend what is read. Literature plays a pivotal role in supporting, sustaining and developing literacy and language learning. Students learn language that is relevant and meaningful for their current and future social interactions through talking, listening, reading and writing. Literature can be regarded as a rich source of "authentic material" because in its written text: one is language in use that is the employment of linguistics by those who have mastered it into a fashion intended for native speakers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE COURSE

The purpose of the study is to investigate the role of literature in supporting language learning. It also objects to examine the alternative techniques to facilitate language learning and teaching through literature.

THE ROLE OF THE LITERATURE IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

The debate about whether or not to include culture in a language classroom is long past; now the discussion points to a matter of method.

Claire Kramsch remarks that it is important to be aware that culture in language learning is not an expandable fifth skill; it is present within writing, reading, listening and speaking. She emphasizes that I am not referring to "institutional" as a pejorative concept but as the most common reading a literary text may have and that sometimes it is taken by some as the proper reading of a work.

When foreign language learners that have been taught the culture alongside

the language encode their messages, they will not do so from a void but from a deep understanding of what they are saying its implications and history. Literature in fact , does not have less meaning than language. According to Widdowson, literature has various meaning depending on the context that the speakers refer to.

It may mean literary writing such as fictions or literature in terms of major of study. Literature referring to literary writing could be defend as aesthetic and moral merit such as those of canon or the great tradition. Or else ,” creative and imaginative” writing (1999, p, 4-5).

Using literary texts in the language classroom can make the students more aware of the language they are learning, help them develop skills and strategies they can apply in many different situations and contexts, increases their interests and motivation, and make the learning of the language more enjoyable . The recent historical positions regarding thr use of literature in english language teaching and the inclusion of literary texts may faster the development of reading, writing , speaking, listening and critical thinking skills. So Literature plays an important role in teaching fou basic language skills like reading, writing, listening, speaking. However , when using literature in the language classroom , skills should never be taught in isolation but in an integrated way. Literature also helps to create empathy and understanding. In fact , according to many literary critics, literature improves theory of mind, which is the capacity to read the minds of others. Encouraging readers to emphathize with fictional , characters, literary narrative cultivates compassion and understanding.

THE ADVANTAGES OF USING LITERARY TEXTS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING CLASSES

Throughout the world, literature is a vital and most prevalent technique that teachers use in their language classes. We mentioned the benefits of literature in receptive and productive language skills as well as vocabulary acquisition.

English literature being affluent and old starting from the eighth century it can aid learners of English as a second language with its diverse themes and rich history. “In many countries around the world students have fairly limited access to speaker English , and written English often takes on primary importance for stimulating language acquisition . Literature may provided a particularly this acquisition as it provide meaningful and memorable contexts for processing and interpreting new language “. (Lazar, 1998,17).

Cultural and social background is another value, where using literary works such as novel , drama , short stories and poetry can be direct input of the culture of the

culture of the English language and society.

CRITERIA FOR SELECTING THE APPROPRIATE LITERARY TEXTS

Regarding the materials or contents of literature it is very essential to know what and what not to include in the language classes selecting the best literature or literary texts in the language classes is very important and teachers have to choose their literary example appropriately and meticulously.

Students' cultural background and their linguistic understandings are also vital. Using short stories in language classes is one of the most widespread technique to which most of the language teachers resort as a powerful means of teaching the language.

CONCLUSION

Literature and culture in ELT provide elements and perspectives through which students cease to regard a foreign language as a harsh and cold code used by people who have little to do with their own context or identity. Literature is a source of authentic material which conveys the use of linguistics by those who have mastered it into a fashion intended for native speakers and an aesthetic representation of the spoken language. Learners are exposed to actual language samples from real life and literature act as a beneficial complement to such materials. Culture offers an interdisciplinary field that includes artistic discourses, social conventions and reflexive impacts. It opens door for students to increase their knowledge of the target culture as they can contemplate and critically comment on people's way of life values, attitudes and beliefs and regard how these elements manifest in linguistic categories and forms.

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